

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

APPLICATION OF ANTHELMINTIC DRUGS AND PLANT MIXTURES CONTAINING ANTHELMINTICS AGAINST NEMATODES AND TREMATODES IN ASSOCIATIVE INVASIONS

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ABSTRACT

The research was carried out with the purpose of learning the helminth fauna of the small ruminants kept in the Shirvan-Salyan and Mountainous-Shirvan economic regions of Azerbaijan. As a result of the research, the taxonomic research of the helminth fauna of the small ruminants was carried out, and the systematics of the species was compiled. The helminths fauna of the sheep and goats - included 32 species nematodes and 3 species of the trematodes in the all economic regions. In the Shirvan-Salyan economic regions the pathogens caused the nematodoses in the animals were the species belonging to the genera *Trichostrongylus*, *Chabertia*, *Oesophagostomum*, *Nematodirus*, *Ostertagia*, *Haemonchus*, *Marshallagia*, *Cooperia*, *Bunostomum*, *Dictyocaulus*, *Protostrongylus*. In the Mountainous-Shirvan economic regions the species belonging to the genera *Dictyocaulus*, *Protostrongylus*, *Muellerius*, *Cystocaulus*, *Trichocephalus*, *Chabertia*, *Oesophagostomum*, *Trichostrongylus*, *Ostertagia*, *Marshallagia*, *Cooperia*, *Haemonchus*, *Bunostomum* and *Nematodirus* were noted with high intensity. In the small ruminants the infection with the nematodes and trematodes was noted with the associative forms in the spring, summer and autumn seasons. For the purpose of deworming 3 anthelmintic preparations 22.2% Fenbendazole, Alvet and Levamin preparations and a mixture of wormwood were tested against the helminthiasis. During the experiment toxicity symptoms were not observed either in the experimental or control animals. A mixture of Alvet and wormwood has been shown to be highly effective against nematodes and trematodes.

Keywords: Wormwood, anthelmintic effectiveness, associative invasions, helminthiasis, pathogenic species.

Introduction

The Shirvan region (the Shirvan-Salyan and Mountainous-Shirvan economic regions), where the research works are conducted, covers the landscapes with the favorable conditions for breeding small-ruminants in the Azerbaijan Republic, and the large animal herds are mainly kept in these areas. The peculiar geographical and ecological features of the region, the relief, as well as the affect of the abiotic and biotic factors were reflected in the formation of the helminth fauna of the small ruminants. So due to the presence of the plains and desert-type landscapes in the region, the helminth fauna consisted mainly of the nematodes in the animals. In the small ruminants the infection with the nematodes and trematodes was noted with the associative forms in the spring, summer and autumn seasons. In the last years, the intensive recording of the parasitic diseases and even deaths in the small-ruminants, and the detection of the parasites belonging to 2 and 3 classes in the animals confirm that the disease agents are in an associative form. The main purpose of the research was the studying the faunistic and systematic composition of the helminths causing the serious pathological processes and death, and the application of the effective treatment measures against the agents. A complex study of the parasitic fauna is important to compile a systematics of the parasites characteristic for the animals kept in a certain area, as well as in the preparation of the effective combat measures against the parasites.

The helminth fauna of the small ruminants is also regularly studied by foreign researchers. The parasitic diseases directly affect the productivity, height and weight development of the animals, that is why their study is always relevant [1, 2, 3, 4]. The natural environmental factors, the geographical and ecological features of the area affect directly the formation of the parasitic fauna of the animals [5].

Anthelmintic chemicals are regularly used against helminthiasis in farm animals. Anthelmintic drugs are not only harmful to helminths, but also toxic to animals. Although the effect of anthelmintic agents in animals is sometimes not clinically evident, it accumulates in the body and has a cumulative effect [6].

For the purpose of deworming 3 anthelmintic preparations 22.2% Fenbendazole, Alvet and Levamin preparations and a mixture of wormwood were tested against the helminthiasis. Wormwood essential oil has bactericidal, bacteriostatic, deodorizing and antiparasitic properties [7, 8]. In veterinary medicine, wormwood is used against helminths in farm animals. Experiments have shown that wormwood has an anthelmintic effect in vitro and in vivo [9].

Material and methods

The researches were carried out in the livestock farms of the Shirvan-Salyan and Mountainous-Shirvan economic regions of Azerbaijan during a year in all the seasons and of all the age groups of the animals. 750 sheep and 450 goats were checked parasitologically in the

Shirvan-Salyan economic region, 1590 sheep and 818 goats in Mountainous-Shirvan. The fecal samples taken from animals were researched by the methods Vishnyauskas, Fullerborn, Berman, Vayda, Darling, Sherbovich. The killed or butchered small-ruminants were researched by the complete and incomplete autopsy method [10, 11, 12]. The classical methods were used for detection the helminths: Macrohelminthoscopy: the detection of the helminth or a segment of a part of it in the fecal mass. Helminthovoscopy: the determination of the helminth

egg by the various methods (the native smear, Fulleborn, Vishnyauskas and repeated washing methods) in the fecal. Helminthylarvoscopy: the tracking of the helminth larvae in the fecal.

The Berman and Vaida methods: the determination of the respiratory tract nematodes (dictiocaulosis and other lung nematodes). The helminthological autopsy method is based on the checking of all the organs of the autopsied dead or butchered animals (Fig. 1.).

Fig. 1. a) Complete autopsy method; b) incomplete autopsy method; c) the research of the fecal samples; d) Collected nematodes

The studies were carried out in all seasons year on nomadic and sedentary livestock farms. Freshwater snails and ants, which are intermediate hosts of trematodes, were studied to determine their species composition. The compressor method was used to study 358 freshwater snails belonging to 7 species, collected from lakes, ditches, and freshwater springs in the study areas. To identify fasciola, dicrocoelium and paramphistomum in slaughtered or dead animals, the liver, stomach, and its departments were opened. Bile samples from the gallbladder were microscopically examined.

Results and discussion

The helminth fauna of the small ruminants which kept in the Shirvan-Salyan economic regions is different. So as non-nomadic farms are mainly moved to pastures in the districts the infection with more nematodes was predominated and observed with varying intensity throughout the year. The high infection was noted in spring, summer, autumn, and the relatively low intensity in winter. It is known that the development and spread of the strongyles is related directly with the climate and humidity conditions [13]. In the recent years, the rainy weather and high humidity have allowed these helminth eggs to remain in an invasive state at all times. Such favorable conditions have caused to the fact that sheep kept in both sedentary

and nomadic farms are infected with geohelminthic nematodes throughout the year. The infection with the trematodes was observed in spring and autumn in the small ruminants which kept on the such livestock farms. In the nomadic farms, the infection with the cestodes was noted more intensive. In the Shirvan-Salyan economic regions the helminth fauna of the small ruminants consisted of 32 species of the nematodes and 3 species of the trematodes. Since the cestodes are found mainly in the nomadic farms, that is why they are not typical species of the small ruminants which kept in these areas. The nematode species of the small ruminants kept in the Shirvan-Salyan economic regions: *Chabertia ovina*, *Bunostomum trigonocephalum*, *Bunostomum phlebotomum*, *Oesophagostomum venulosum*, *Oesophagostomum columbianum*, *Trichostrongylus axei*, *Trichostrongylus capricola*, *Trichostrongylus colubriformis*, *Trichostrongylus probulurus*, *Trichostrongylus skrjabini*, *Trichostrongylus vitrinus*, *Trichostrongylus assadovi*, *Trichostrongylus ostertagi*, *Ostertagia circumcincta*, *Ostertagia trifurcata*, *Ostertagia mentulata*, *Marshallagia marshalli*, *Cooperia oncophora*, *Haemonchus contortus*, *Nematodirus abnormalis*, *Nematodirus helvetianus*, *Trichocephalus ovis*, *Trichocephalus skrjabini*, *Gongylonema*

pulchrum, *Dictyocaulus filaria*, *Protostrongylus hobmaieri*, *Protostrongylus kochi*, *Protostrongylus davtian*, *Protostrongylus raillieti*, *Protostrongylus skrjabini*, *Muellerius capillaris*, *Cystocaulus nigrescens* helminths have been identified. *Bunostomum phlebotomum* helminth was not found in sheep and *Trichostrongylus assadovi* helminth was not found in goats. The causative agents detected in sheep and goats with high intensity and causing the helminthiasis were nematodes belonging to the *Chabertia* (length 131.0; width 64.0 um), *Oesophagostomum* (length 77.0; width 47.9 um),

Nematodirus (length 180.0; width 78.1.0 um), *Ostertagia spp* (length 81.1; width 67.7 um), *Haemonchus sp.* (length 77.6; width 47.7 um), *Marshallagia sp.* (length 184.0; width 76.2 um), *Cooperia sp.* (length 79.5; width 48.6 um), *Trichostrongylus* (length 67.6 width 42.1 um), *Bunostomum* (length 75.0; width 47,3 um), *Dictyocaulus* (length 88.7; width 49.5 um), *Protostrongylus* (length 89.0; width 68.7 um) genera. The infection of animals with nematodes was 76.8%, the intensity was 31-252 ind. The discovered nematode eggs are shown in figure 2.

Fig 2. a) *Chabertia ovina*; b) *Oesophagostomum sp.*; c) *Nematodirus sp.*; d) *Ostertagia sp.*; e) *Haemonchus sp.*; f) *Protostrongylus sp.*; g) *Cooperia sp.*; h) *Trichostrongylus sp.*; i) *Dictyocaulus sp.*

The pathogenic species belonging to the class of trematodes were detected in the animals kept in the Kura-Araz lowland areas, and the species composition was determined in the small ruminants. Causative agents of the trematodes are mainly localized in the liver and cause mass loss during intensive infection. *Fasciola hepatica* belonging to the genus *Fasciola* of the family Fasciolidae belonging to the class Trematodes, *Dicrocoelium lanceatum* belonging to the genus

Dicrocoelium of the family Dicrocoeliidae, *Paramphistomum cervi* helminth belonging to the genus *Paramphistomum* of the family Paramphistomatidae were detected which grown in the Shirvan-Salyan economic regions, characteristic for these areas in the small ruminants. *Fasciola hepatica*, *Dicrocoelium lanceatum* and *Paramphistomum cervi* intensively noted trematodoses in the plain landscapes of the region (Fig. 3.).

Fig. 3. *Paramphistomum cervi*

Dicrocoelium lanceatum

Fasciola hepatica

The intensive distribution of the intermediate hosts, as well as climate and humidity, resulted in the

infection of the animals of all the age groups of the trematodes in all the seasons of the year. The discovered trematode eggs are shown in figure 4.

Fig 4. a) *Dicrocoelium* sp.

b) *Fasciola* sp.

c) *Paramphistomum* sp.

The intensity of fasciola and dicrocoelium helminths isolated from the liver during grain research in sheep and goats was 17-185 individuals. The intensity of paramphistomum collected from the stomach sections was 45-96 individuals higher in sheep and 25-137 individuals in goats. This indicates that fasciolosis, dicrocoeliosis and paramphistomosis are widespread in the studied areas. Infection with helminths in small ruminants is associated with associative forms - gastrointestinal and respiratory nematodes and trematodes in spring, summer and autumn. The analogous researches were conducted in the Mountainous Shirvan economic regions. The Mountainous Shirvan economic region (Ismayilli, Shamakhi, Aghsu, Gobustan) covers the plains, foothills (Gobustan and Aghsu) and mountainous areas (Shamakhi and Ismayilli), that is why the parasite fauna of the small-ruminants was relatively different. The endoparasites of sheep and goats consisted of 32 nematodes species, 4 trematodes species. The infection occurred in an associative form (in both landscapes). The species belonging to the genera *Dictyocaulus*, *Protostrongylus*, *Muellerius*, *Cystocaulus*, *Trichocephalus*, *Chabertia*, *Oesophagostomum*, *Trichostrongylus*, *Ostertagia*, *Marshallagia*, *Cooperia*, *Haemonchus*, *Bunostomum* and *Nematodirus* were noted with high intensity. *Fasciola hepatica*, *F. gigantica* helminths belonging to the *Fasciola* genus of the

Fasciolidae family, *Dicrocoelium lanceatum* helminths belonging to the *Dicrocoeliidae* family, and *Paramphistomum cervi* trematodes belonging to the *Paramphistomum* genus caused intensively noted trematodosis in the foothills and plain landscapes of the region. The intensive distribution of the intermediate hosts, as well as climate and humidity, resulted in the infection of the animals of all the age groups of the trematodes in all the seasons of the year. There are ponds enough in the areas of the Mountainous Shirvan economic region, that is why, this caused the population density of the intermediate hosts of the trematodes - molluscs. The infection with the trematodes was observed with the low intensity due to the seasonal changes (with the low intensity in late spring and summer) in the mountainous landscapes of the territory (Ismayilli, Shamakhi). In our researches, the secondary infectious origin diseases were observed in 80% of the animals infected with the trematodosis had diseases of secondary infection (pleuropneumonia, enterotoxemia, etc.). In the Shirvan-Salyan and Mountain Shirvan economic regions, in the small-ruminants, the infection with the helminths in the associative form were observed in spring, summer and the first decade of autumn. In winter, in sheep and goats, the infection only with the gastrointestinal and respiratory tract nematodes were observed (Fig. 5.).

Fig. 5. Associative nematode and trematodes

We analyze the composition of the parasite fauna of the small ruminants in the economic regions and come to the conclusion that the infection of the animals with the nematodes and trematodes is observed with the different intensity throughout the year in both regions.

Conclusions

Experiments have shown that wormwood has an anthelmintic effect in vitro and in vivo Purpose - to study the effectiveness of wormwood and anthelmintic mixtures. The experimental animals were divided into four groups according to weight and age groups. The

first group of animals was given a mixture of wormwood and 22.2% Fenbendazole in equal doses of 200 g per day for two days. The second group of animals was given a mixture of Levamine and 200 g of wormwood. The third group of animals was given a mixture of Alvet - wormwood. The mixture given to the animals consisted of 0.5 g of the preparation and 200 g of wormwood. Fourthly, the animals of the control group were not given the drug and were fed as usual. Animal samples were taken and laboratory tests were performed 10 days after ingestion. In the field of view of the microscope, the animals of the first group had 2-4 parasite eggs, the animals of the second group had 1-3 parasite eggs and the animals of the third group had 0-1 parasite egg (trematode eggs appeared, there were no nematode eggs) In group IV, 8-15 parasite eggs were seen in the field of view of the microscope (there were no changes).

The mixture of Alvet + wormwood was repeated to animals against trematodes after 15 days. The results of the study show that the mixture of wormwood and Alvet has a high anthelmintic effect against nematodes and trematodes that parasitize the digestive and respiratory systems of animals. Signs of toxicity in experimental and control animals were not observed during the experiment. This fact indicates that both wormwood and its mixture with Alvet can be used against nematodes and trematodes.

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